

Physico-chemical Investigations on the Reactions of Benzamidothiosemicarbazide with Zn(II) and Cd(II)

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The reaction of Zn(II) and Cd(II) with benzamidothiosemicarbazide was studied by various physico-chemical methods. Electrometric studies and chemical analysis gave 1 : 2 metal-ligand ratio. The average values of stepwise stability constants and overall stability constants, $\log K_1 = 4.39$, $\log K_2 = 3.80$ and $\log K = 8.19$ for Zn(II); $\log K_1 = 4.80$, $\log K_2 = 4.09$ and $\log K = 8.89$ for Cd(II) complexes, respectively were determined pH-metrically, keeping temperature ($30 \pm 1^\circ$) and ionic strength (0.08 M) constant. These complexes were isolated and characterised by magnetic and spectral studies.

WE have earlier reported^{1,2} the studies on the complexes of Cu(II), Hg(II) and Pb(II) with benzamidothiosemicarbazide (BTSC). The results of our studies on the composition and structural characteristics of Zn(II) and Cd(II) complexes with BTSC are described here.

Experimental

Benamidothiosemicarbazide (BTSC) solution was prepared in ethyl alcohol-water (80 : 20 v/v) mixture. Fresh solution of BTSC was always used. Stock solutions of Zn(II) and Cd(II) acetate were prepared by dissolving the salts in air free double distilled water. The strength of these solutions was determined by the usual methods.

Conductometric titrations of BTSC against Zn(II) and Cd(II) were carried out to determine stoichiometry of these complexes. A series of mixture of solutions according to the monovariation method, keeping the concentration of BTSC constant and varying the metal (direct titration) and *vice versa* (reverse titration) were prepared, keeping the total volume the same in each case. The plots of conductance vs concentration of metal (or ligand) gave inflections corresponding to metal-ligand interaction ratio in the complex.

A series of equimolecular mixtures (0.02 M), keeping the ligand constant (in excess) and varying the metal (1.0, 1.5, 2.0 and 4.0 ml) was prepared. The total volume (30 ml) of each solution was kept constant. Each solution was titrated with 0.04 M KOH and the corresponding conductance noted. The corrected conductance values were plotted against moles of KOH (Figs. 1, 2). Blank titrations for metal and ligand, keeping the total volume the same, were also carried out. Philips

conductivity bridge with dip type conductivity cell was used in determining the conductance.

Fig. 1. Curve 1. 1.0 ml of Zn acetate + 8.0 ml of BTSC.
Curve 2. 2.0 ml of Zn acetate + 8.0 ml of BTSC.
Curve 3. 3.0 ml of Zn acetate + 8.0 ml of BTSC.
Curve 4. 4.0 ml of Zn acetate + 8.0 ml of BTSC.
Curve 5. 0.0 ml of Zn acetate + 4.0 ml of BTSC.

Amperometric titrations were carried out on a manual polarograph in conjunction with Pye scalamp galvanometer. Both direct and reverse titrations were performed using 0.02 M solutions of metal and ligand in presence of 0.02 M KCl as supporting electrolyte and 0.008% solution of gelatin as maximum suppressor. Purified nitrogen was bubbled through the solution for about 10 min before starting the titrations and for about 1

min after each addition of the titrant. The titrations were carried out at constant potential (-0.15 volt) using d.m.e. against SCE. The observed diffusion currents were corrected for dilution and plotted against the volume of metal (or ligand) to give metal-ligand interaction ratio.

Fig. 2. Curve 1. 1.0 ml of Cd acetate + 8.0 ml of BTSC.
 Curve 2. 1.5 ml of Cd acetate + 8.0 ml of BTSC.
 Curve 3. 2.0 ml of Cd acetate + 8.0 ml of BTSC.
 Curve 4. 4.0 ml of Cd acetate + 8.0 ml of BTSC.

Elico-pH meter with glass electrode and SCE was used for pH measurements. KOH solution (0.1 M) was added to the reaction mixture from a microburette (least count 0.05 ml). All the pH measurements were performed at constant temperature (30 ± 1°) using Toshniwal thermostatic bath. KCl 'AR' grade was used to maintain constant ionic strength.

The isolation of the complexes was carried out as described below.

Equimolecular solutions (0.02 M) of the metal salt and BTSC were mixed with stirring in 1 : 2 ratio. The resulting solutions were concentrated over water bath, when solid separated quickly. The solids were cooled, filtered, washed with cold water, recrystallised with hot methanol and finally dried in a vacuum desiccator. The isolated complexes were analysed for elements and the results are given in Table 1.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Complex	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)					
	Metal	Carbon	Hydrogen	Sulphur	Nitrogen	Oxygen
ZnX	12.58 (12.56)	36.96 (36.96)	4.27 (4.27)	12.33 (12.33)	21.55 (21.55)	12.31 (12.31)
CdX	19.82 (19.83)	33.89 (33.90)	3.93 (3.92)	11.31 (11.31)	19.77 (19.77)	11.29 (11.29)

X = (O₁₆H₂₂N₆O₄S₂).

The ir spectra of Zn(II) and Cd(II) complexes were taken in KBr medium by the method of fast scanning using Beckman IR 20 spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

Preliminary studies showed that aqueous solution of Zn(II) and Cd(II) acetate mixed with a solution of BTSC gave immediately white precipitates. Results of conductometric titrations of metal-ligand mixtures against KOH showed liberations of protons during complexation.

Normal conductometric curves (monovariation method) were obtained for Zn(II) and Cd(II). In all the cases sharp breaks corresponding to 1 : 2 metal-ligand ratio were observed for both direct and reverse titrations. Titration curves 1-3 (Figs. 1, 2) showed two breaks first corresponded to 1 : 2 stoichiometry and the second due to the neutralisation of unused excess of the ligand in 1 : 1 ratio as obtained in the titration of ligand alone (curve 5, Fig. 1). It was also observed that titration curve 4 (Figs. 1, 2), where ligand was not in excess but was in 1 : 2 ratio, showed single break. In each case, the slight increase in conductance was due to the replacement of M²⁺ by K⁺ ions forming potassium acetate and the H⁺ ions from the ligand being removed as water. Thereafter, upto the second end point, conductance was due to the formation of more ionisable potassium salt of ligand. Beyond the second break, the sharp increase was due to free KOH.

BTSC gave oxidation currents* (E_{1/2} = -0.1 volt). Therefore, a constant potential of -0.15 volt was applied for all amperometric titrations. At this potential Zn(II) and Cd(II) gave no current. Normal curves were obtained and gave sharp breaks confirming the stoichiometry observed in conductometric studies.

The pK value (8.1) of the BTSC, determined pH-metrically was in agreement with the value obtained polarographically. pH-Titrations performed with mixtures of metal-ligand, ligand and metal separately against 0.1 M KOH showed lowering of pH, indicating liberation of protons as a result of complex formation. Maximum lowering of pH in case of 1 : 2 metal-BTSC mixture and the inflection corresponding to 2 moles of KOH : 1 mole of metal salt further support the 1 : 2 metal-ligand ratio of the complex.

At constant temperature and constant ionic strength (0.08 M), pH-titrations of BTSC alone and in presence of different concentration of metal ions, performed according to the method of Calvin and Melchior⁴, gave normal pH-metric curves when titrated against 0.1 M KOH. From these curves, different sets of \bar{n} values at various pH were determined and the corresponding concentrations of free ligand (\bar{A}) were calculated. The value of \bar{n} were plotted against the corresponding values of pA or -log A (Figs. 3, 4). As a first approximation the value of pA at $\bar{n}=0.5$ and at $\bar{n}=1.5$ gave stepwise stability constants, log K₁ and log K₂, respectively and summation of the two gave overall stability constant (log K). The average values of stepwise stability constant and overall stability constant, log K₁=4.39, log K₂=3.80 and log K=8.19 for Zn(II);

$\log K_1=4.80$, $\log K_2=4.09$ and $\log K=8.89$ for Cd(II), were obtained. It is clear from these measurements that \bar{n} increases with the increase of pH, showing thereby that it is the anionic form of the ligand which takes part in the reaction.

Fig. 3. Formation curves for Zn-BTSC complex.

Fig. 4. Formation curves for Cd-BTSC complex.

Results of chemical analysis (Table 1) further supported the stoichiometric ratio obtained from electrometric studies, suggesting the molecular formulae of $Zn(C_{16}H_{22}N_8O_4S_2)$ and $Cd(C_{16}H_{22}N_8O_4S_2)$ to these complexes, respectively. The Cd complex melts at $270 \pm 1^\circ$ while the Zn complex turned brown at 300° and did not melt upto 360° .

The ir absorption bands at 3280, 3180 and 3100 cm^{-1} observed in the spectrum of BTSC were due to the NH and NH_2 stretching vibrations. In the spectra of Zn(II) and Cd(II) complexes, these bands were broadened and shifted to higher frequencies of 3400-3480, 3340, 3200-3280 cm^{-1} and 3420-3500, 3320, 3180 cm^{-1} , respectively, suggesting that NH_2 group of hydrazine was not involved in complex formation⁵⁻⁷. The broadness of some of these bands was a clear indication that these vibrations were effected by some other vibrational modes, probably -OH, of the attached water molecule⁷. Furthermore, two sharp bands at 3660 and 1620 cm^{-1} in Zn(II) complex and at 3660 and 1615 cm^{-1} in Cd(II) complex supported the presence of coordinated water in these complexes. The former being due to antisymmetric and symmetric O-H stretching modes and the latter corresponding to H-O-H bonding modes. Thermogravimetric

analysis further supported the presence of coordinated water. Moreover, no loss in weight was observed when these complexes were placed over conc. H_2SO_4 for several hr in vacuum desiccator, showing bonded water in these complexes.

The absorption bands at 1630 cm^{-1} occurring in the ligand spectrum was due to the bending vibrations of the amino and the amide groups. The appearance of the amide band at higher frequency at 1670 and 1645 cm^{-1} in Zn(II) and Cd(II) complexes, respectively (instead of decrease) indicated non-participation of the amide nitrogen atom. However, its intensity was affected due to the presence of water molecule in the complex. Furthermore, lowering of NCS bend frequency occurring at 1180 to 1160 and 1150 cm^{-1} in Zn(II) and Cd(II), respectively suggested the involvement of nitrogen atom (attached to the amide nitrogen atom) in bond formation.

The absorption bands in BTSC occurring at 1318, 790 and 760 cm^{-1} was assigned to C=S stretching frequency. Similar assignments have been made for thioacetamide and other thiocompounds^{8,9}. One more band at 1060 cm^{-1} for C=S stretching has been reported in xanthates^{10,11}. In the spectra of the metal complexes, these bands showed a shift to the lower wavelengths due to the binding of sulphur to the metal¹². These bands appeared at 1290, 1050, 775 and 745 cm^{-1} in Zn(II) and 1280, 1045, 775 and 740 cm^{-1} in Cd(II) complexes indicating the presence of coordinated sulphur. The absence of bands in the ligand spectrum and appearance of new bands occurring at 440 and 430 cm^{-1} were due to M-N, at 340 cm^{-1} and 330 cm^{-1} to M-O and weak absorption bands at 280 and 295 cm^{-1} may be assigned to M-S bands in Zn(II) and Cd(II) complexes, respectively.

Like other complexes of Zn^{2+} and Cd^{2+} with O, N and S containing ligands, these complexes were also found to be diamagnetic and hexacoordinated having the following formula and structure.

$[R = C_6H_5CONH; M = Zn(II) \text{ or } Cd(II)]$
 Formula : $MX_2 \cdot 2H_2O$; $(X = C_6H_5N_2OS)$

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